

Surface area of Indian Clay Minerals

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A literature survey reveals that a great deal of work has been done on clay minerals of different countries from the point of view of surface area, pore size distribution, carriers and their catalytic activity¹⁻⁷. Indian clay minerals on the other hand have mainly been studied from the point of view of particle size and structure and little work appears to have been done on surface area, pore size distribution and catalytic activity. Hence it has been thought worthwhile to make a systematic study on the Indian mineral clays. This paper, therefore, first presents the surface area of Indian mineral clays which might help us in elucidating the catalytic activity of clay minerals.

Experimental

The surface area of Indian mineral clays have been determined by BET volumetric gas adsorption method which has been described elsewhere⁸.

Adsorbents: Indian clay samples, representative of several of the most common clay minerals types were selected, namely: kaolinite, bentonite, montmorillonite, pyrophyllite, chrysolite, vernaculite and talc. These samples were purchased from the Indian commercial firms.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 summarizes the values of surface area for Indian mineral clays which were calculated from the linear portion (partial pressure, P_e/P_0 , 0.05-0.35) of the BET plot.

TABLE I

Clay minerals	Nitrogen area, V_m sq.m/g.
1. Kaolinite	10.4
2. TALC	20.3
3. Chrysolite	22.1
4. Montmorillonite	38.9
5. Pyrophyllite	49.8
6. Vernaculite	55.3
7. Bentonite	67.7

The surface areas presented in the above table was determined after degassing the clay samples at 200° for 5 hrs. This was done in order to remove the adsorbed water and adsorbed gases from the clay samples. The surface areas were found to have little higher values when compared with the clays of other countries⁹⁻¹¹. The difference may be attributed to the fineness of the clay particles or porous nature of the Indian clays.

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Potentiometric studies of N-benzoylacetone- β -alanine (Schiff base) complexes of La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III) and Nd(III)

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PROTONATION constants of the Schiff base derived from benzoylacetone and β -alanine, and the formation constants of its complexes with trivalent metal ions have been determined potentiometrically in 50% (vol./vol.) dioxan solutions ($\mu = 0.1M$ NaClO₄) at 30° ± 0.1°. The order of stability constants was found to be La(III) < Ce(III) < Pr(III) < Nd(III). Free energy changes of the complexation reaction have also been evaluated.

The dissociation constants of N-benzoylacetone- β -alanine (abbr. H₂B β A) and the formation constants of its complexes with La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III) and Nd(III) are reported in this paper.

All the chemicals used were either B.D.H. AnalaR or Riedel reagents. The ligand was synthesised by the method reported earlier¹ and its standard solutions were prepared in dioxan. The metal nitrate solutions were prepared in double distilled water. pH of the solution was measured by employing DORAN pH-meter No. 3078.

Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique²⁻³ as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁴ was adopted for obtaining

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stepwise stability constants of the complexes $\%NaClO_4$ solution (0.1M) was used to maintain the constant ionic strength and the reaction solutions were thermostated at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$.

In the case of $H_2B\beta A$ the formation curve extends upto $\bar{n}_A = 1.9$ suggesting that two protons respectively from carboxylic and enolic groups are dissociated. The protonation constants thus obtained are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF $H_2B\beta A$

Temp. = $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$			
$\mu = 0.1M$ ($NaClO_4$)			
Method	$\log K_1^H$	$\log K_2^H$	$\log \beta_2^H = \log K_1^H K_2^H$
Interpolation at half $\bar{n}_A$ values			
	10.50	5.50	16.00
Interpolation at various $\bar{n}_A$ values			
	10.33 (10.42)	5.48 (5.49)	15.81 (15.91)
Average values are given in parentheses.			

The formation curves (Fig. 1) of all the metal-ligand systems attain maxima at $\bar{n}_A > 1.5$ indicating that 1:1 and 1:2 complexes are formed. The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were calculated from the

Fig. 1. Formation curves of trivalent metal- $H_2B\beta A$ systems.

formation curves at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and $\bar{n} = 1.5$ respectively. The values of these constants were refined by interpolation at various $\bar{n}$ values, interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values⁵, correction term method, successive approximation method and convergence formulae⁶ as shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF TRIVALENT METAL COMPLEXES WITH $H_2B\beta A$

	A	B	C	D	E	F	$-\Delta F$ (K.cal/mole)
La(III)							
$\log K_1$	6.24	6.07	6.08	6.04	6.04	6.09	15.50
$\log K_2$	4.95	5.11	5.11	5.14	5.14	5.09	
Ce(III)							
$\log K_1$	6.66	6.42	6.46	6.37	6.37	6.46	16.55
$\log K_2$	5.28	5.51	5.48	5.56	5.56	5.48	
Pr(III)							
$\log K_1$	7.14	6.90	6.84	6.83	6.83	6.91	18.07
$\log K_2$	5.90	6.13	6.21	6.20	6.20	6.13	
Nd(III)							
$\log K_1$	7.84	7.62	7.69	7.61	7.61	7.67	19.33
$\log K_2$	6.20	6.27	6.35	6.28	6.28	6.28	

A = interpolation at various $\bar{n}$ values; B = interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values; C = correction term method; D = successive approximation method; E = convergence formulae method; F = average value, and ΔF = overall change in free energy.

$H_2B\beta A$ being a biprotic tridentate neutralises two equivalents of the base to yield two buffer regions in its potentiometric equilibrium curve

when 5:1 mixtures of ligand to metal are titrated against standard alkali the systems show inflections at lower buffer region indicating complexation. The complex equilibria may be represented by the equations

La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III) and Nd(III) having $4f^0$, $4f^1$, $4f^2$ and $4f^3$ electrons possess ionic radii 1.061, 1.034, 1.013 and 0.995Å respectively and the stability of the complexes of the metal, having similar electronic configuration, increases with decreasing ionic size. The same trend has also been observed in the present case.

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Amperometric Estimation of Copper with Benzimidazole-2-Carboxylic Acid

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BENZIMIDAZOLE-2-carboxylic acid has been utilized as a reagent for amperometric estimation of copper. A manual polarographic set complete with potentiometer and a suitable spot-reflecting galvanometer as the current-measuring device was used for the titrations and for recording polarograms. A buffer solution containing 0.1M sodium acetate and 0.1M acetic acid (pH 4.6) has been found to be the most appropriate medium for conducting the titrations, in which copper is quantitatively precipitated by this reagent. The use of a little gelatine (0.01%) in the titrating solution serves as a maximum-suppressor. The titrations are best carried out at a potential of -0.5 volt (vs. S.C.E.) using dropping mercury electrode at which the diffusion current due to the reaction $\text{Cu(II)} \rightarrow \text{Cu(O)}$ is fully developed, whereas the reagent suffers very little change.

Benzimidazole-2-carboxylic acid was prepared and purified by the method described in literature¹. The reagent solutions (0.1M and 0.025M) were prepared in 1:1 aqueous ethanol containing calculated amount of KOH to effect the solution of the reagent. The strength of the copper solution was verified iodometrically. For the purpose of amperometric titrations, a number of copper solutions containing varying copper concentrations were prepared from definite aliquot portions of the standard copper solution, the buffer solution and the gelatine solution. Titrations were conducted at room temperature (~30°). The end-point was accurately determined by the graphical method from the point of intersection of two arms of an L-shaped curve (Fig. 1), obtained by plotting the galvanometer deflections (current values) against the volume of the reagent solution added, applying the usual volume corrections to account for the dilution effect of the titrating solution. Copper solutions containing 6 mg. to 2 mg. copper were titrated with 0.1M reagent solution, whereas those from 1 mg. to 0.5 mg. with 0.025M reagent solution. Some typical results are shown in the Table 1. Copper can be estimated by this method in presence of appreciable amounts of

metallic ions like Zn^{++} , Mn^{++} , Co^{++} , Ni^{++} , Cd^{++} , Pb^{++} , Ca^{++} , Mg^{++} , Al^{+++} and Fe^{+++} without any

Fig. 1

A typical curve of amperometric titration of copper(II) solution with benzimidazole-2-carboxylic acid.

V = initial volume of Cu(II) solution titrated.

v = volume of titre solution added.

The upward arrow indicates the equivalent of actual copper content.

TABLE 1—AMPEROMETRIC TITRATION OF COPPER WITH BENZIMIDAZOLE-2-CARBOXYLIC ACID

Total volume titrated = 15 ml.

Present (mg)	Copper	
	Found (mg)	Error (%)
6.00	6.01	+0.17
4.00	4.00	0.00
2.00	2.00	0.00
1.00	1.00	0.00
0.50	0.498	-0.40

interference. Copper was estimated in presence of Fe^{+++} by adding sufficient amount of $(\text{NH}_4)\text{HF}_2$ before titration. For titration in presence of Pb^{++} and Ni^{++} , a different buffer solution containing 0.05M sodium acetate and 0.95M acetic acid (pH 3.4) was used.

The above titration procedure was applied with satisfactory results in the estimation of copper in a sample of standard leaded brass having the composition: Cu, 59.82%; Zn, 34.95%; Fe, 0.82%; Pb, 3.54%; Sn, 0.80%.

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